

Developments in digital scholarship: at the British Library and at kitchen tables everywhere

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With thanks to... teamwork

The Digital Research Team is a cross-disciplinary mix of curators, researchers, librarians and programmers supporting the creation and innovative use of British Library's digital collections.

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@benosteen @mahendra_mahey

Supporting digital scholarship @ BL

We support new ways of exploring and accessing our collections through:

- Getting digital and digitised content available online
- Collaborative projects
- Digital scholarship support and guidance
- Events, publications and training
- Competitions, and awards (BL Labs)

FIG. 155.—JANUS.

LIBRARY
HSILIRB

British Library Labs
Experiment with our
digital collections

<http://labs.bl.uk>

Living Knowledge: The British Library 2015 – 2023

CUSTODIANSHIP

RESEARCH

BUSINESS

CULTURE

LEARNING

INTERNATIONAL

'We make our intellectual heritage accessible to everyone, for research, inspiration and enjoyment'

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Ok, but how?

Internal digital scholarship training

Evaluating the training programme: goals

- Staff across all collection areas are familiar and conversant with the foundational concepts, methods and tools of digital scholarship.
- Staff are empowered to innovate.
- Collaborative digital initiatives flourish across subject areas within the Library as well as externally.
- Our internal capacity for training and skill-sharing in digital scholarship are a shared responsibility across the Library.

Participants appreciated...

- Hands-on, practical exercises
- Time to explore innovative digital projects
- Trying new tools, particularly with BL or similar collections
- The expertise and enthusiasm of instructors
- Meeting colleagues and learning about BL projects

Practical digital training tips

- Case studies / real world examples help
- Articulate learning outcomes, expected results for exercises
- Provide clear, printable instructions
- No more than 15 people in hands-on courses
- Allow time for all to complete exercises
- Build in optional activities for advanced participants

Inspired... Big Data History of Music

How can vast amounts of bibliographic data held by research libraries be unlocked for music researchers to analyse?

Analyses and visualisations of these datasets exposed previously uncharted patterns in the history of music.

On-going challenges

- Applying new skills within the Library - more guidance and support within current Library policy and infrastructure
- Reaching staff who work on rosters and cannot attend for a whole day
- Digital tools for non-Western materials; working with non-textual digital collections such as the UK Web and Sound Archives

Challenge: the pace of change

- Software tools break/change - some courses need to be completely checked before they're run
- Digital Curators need to maintain our skills and knowledge too
 - Digital Scholarship Reading Group - 1 hour, once a month
 - Hack and Yack - 2 hours, once a month
 - Both are open to all

Transkribus for handwritten text recognition

Document metadata

Loaded doc: OCR Sample Document - Gothic f
Current collection: Transkribus Cloud, ID: 4
Current file: 420000317426_J.Ritter_Briefe_0000
Key: IAZSJCHTXHCUXLQRMIBNWXN

Document metadata... Editorial Declaration...

Logged in as: mia.ridge@bl.uk
Server: https://transkribus.eu/TrpServer

Server documents

Collections:

Transkribus Cloud (4, Transcriber)

Documents:

1-3 / 3

ID	Title	N-Pages
558	OCR Sample Documen...	12
1927	HTR_Reichsgericht	10
3768	Missiven 3221	162

Line based | Region:

HTR suggestions: CATTI

Datasets and digital collections

[Datasets about our collections](#)

Bibliographic datasets relating to our published and archival holdings

[Datasets for content mining](#) Content suitable for use in text and data mining research

[Datasets for image analysis](#) Image collections suitable for large-scale image-analysis-based research

[Datasets from UK Web Archive](#) Data and API services available for accessing UK Web Archive collections

[Digital mapping](#) Geospatial data, cartographic applications, digital aerial photography and scanned-in historic map materials

The screenshot shows the 'DIGITISED MANUSCRIPTS' website. At the top right is a 'Quick Search' input field. Below it is a navigation menu with links for 'Home', 'About', 'Browse', 'Search', and 'Help'. A search button labeled 'Search the British Library website' is on the right. The main content area has a breadcrumb trail: 'bl.uk > Digitised Manuscripts Home > About'. The 'About' section contains a paragraph about the site's content and a 'Highlights' sidebar. The sidebar features three items: 'The St Cuthbert Gospel' with an image of a wooden cover, 'Theodore Psalter' with an image of a manuscript page, and 'Bach' with an image of musical notation. The 'Greek Manuscripts' section describes over 600 manuscripts from the 9th to 18th centuries. The 'Harley Scientific Manuscripts' section describes 150 medieval and modern scientific manuscripts. The 'Royal Illuminated Manuscripts' section describes 2,000 manuscripts from the 17th century.

DIGITISED MANUSCRIPTS

Quick Search

Home About Browse Search Help Search the British Library website

bl.uk > Digitised Manuscripts Home > About

About

The Digitised Manuscripts site contains many different kinds of manuscripts, archives and documents. Much of the content available here has been digitised as part of the British Library's digitisation projects, details of which are given below.

Greek Manuscripts

There are more than 600 Greek manuscripts ranging in date from the 9th century to the 18th century included in the Digitised Manuscripts site. These were digitised during two phases of a project funded generously by the Stavros Niarchos Foundation between 2008 and 2010.

They include manuscripts from the British Library's Additional, Harley, Arundel and Royal manuscript collections, which demonstrate the range of Greek manuscripts, and include some of the highlights of the Library's collections. The British Library holds approximately 1,000 Greek manuscripts, and intends to digitise the remainder in the next three years. Newly digitised Greek manuscripts will be announced on the Medieval and Earlier Manuscripts Blog.

Harley Scientific Manuscripts

The Harley Science Project, funded by William and Judith Bollinger, makes available images and descriptions of 150 medieval and modern scientific manuscripts from the British Library's Harley collection. The Project also incorporates updated records of seventy-two medical manuscripts that were created in 2005–2007 for the Harley Medical Manuscripts Catalogue funded by the Wellcome Trust.

The Harley collection, created by the statesman Robert Harley (1661–1724) and his son Edward Harley, is particularly rich in scientific material. The manuscripts selected for the project range in date from the 9th century to the 17th century, and are written in a variety of European languages (including Latin, Old and Middle English, Middle Dutch, Anglo-Norman and Old French, German, Irish, Italian and Spanish). They comprise texts relating to early scientific knowledge, such as astronomy, astrology, the computus, mathematics, physics, botany, medicine and veterinary science.

Royal Illuminated Manuscripts

In 1757 King George II presented approximately 2,000 manuscripts to the newly

Highlights

-
The St Cuthbert Gospel
-
Theodore Psalter
-
Bach

<http://bl.uk/digital>

COLLECTION METADATA

Data Services

Home > Collection Metadata > Data Services > Downloads

Downloads

Bulk downloads, serialized as [N-Triples](#), [RDF/XML](#) or [CSV](#) are available below. These may be downloaded as compressed files (ZIP format).

Files are distributed under a [Creative Commons CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication](#) licence. For further details about our terms and conditions, please see [here](#).

Linked Open Data

- **British National Bibliography**

Books and serials eligible for BNB. Models, schema and URI patterns available [here](#). Updated monthly. Zipped folders include multiple files and a PDF document.

DATASET	DATE	SIZE (KB) <i>(full file)</i>	FULL FILE	SAMPLE
BNB LOD Books	2016-05	1,080,387	nt	nt
BNB LOD Serials	2016-05	41,936	nt	nt
BNB LOD Books	2016-05	1,102,362	rdxml	rdxml
BNB LOD Serials	2016-05	36,692	rdxml	rdxml
VoID Descriptions	2016-05	5	ttl	N/A

Search service: <http://bnb.data.bl.uk>
 SPARQL editor: <http://bnb.data.bl.uk/flint-sparql>
 SPARQL endpoint: <http://bnb.data.bl.uk/sparql>

Open Data: basic RDF/XML

Sections:

British National Bibliography

Data Services

> [Free data](#)

> [Sample data](#)

> [Downloads](#)

Standards

News

Contact us

This page contains links to Adobe PDF files. [Accessibility solutions](#) and free 'Reader' software are available from Adobe.

<http://www.bl.uk/bibliographic/download.html>

[home](#)

- JISC UK WEB DOMAIN DATASET (1996-2013)
 - [Introduction](#)
 - [Format Profile](#)
 - [Geoindex](#)
 - [Host-level Links](#)
 - [Crawled URL Index](#)
- UK SELECTIVE WEB ARCHIVE
 - [Introduction](#)
 - [Website Classification Dataset](#)
- PROJECTS
 - [Big UK Domain Data for the Arts and Humanities](#)
 - [Analytical Access to the Domain Dark Archive](#)
 - [Big Data: Demonstrating the Value of the UK Web Domain Dataset for Social Science Research](#)
 - [SCAPE: Scaleable Preservation Environments](#)
- RELATED WORK
 - [Common Crawl](#)
 - [httparchive.org](#)

UK Web Archive Open Data

In order to facilitate research, and so we might better understand and preserve the UK's web history, the UK Web Archive has decided to make a number of data and API services available for general use. We also make a few example tools available, showing how the open data might be used, and these are hosted in this GitHub repository.

We hope that by making these datasets available, the broader community will find interesting ways to re-use, explore and visualise the contents of our web archive. We are keen to work with any interested parties to exploit these datasets, and understand what other derivative or summary data would be of interest.

Datasets, Tools & APIs

Open Datasets

In general, we can't provide remote bulk access to the primary datasets listed above (although bulk access can be arranged for particular projects - see below). This is mainly because the conditions underwhich we hold the content do not permit it, but also because the data sets are very large and so providing bulk downloads is not practical.

However, secondary datasets, composed of metadata that describes simple facts about the content, can be made available under open terms.

For all the details, follow the links on the left, or look through the README files and code in [the GitHub repository](#).

Tools

We also make a few tools available, which illustrate how the open datasets might be used. These are hosted on GitHub, and you should feel free to fork our repository or download our tools using the links above. Pull requests containing new or improved tools are welcome!

<http://data.webarchive.org.uk/>

data.bl.uk

data.bl.uk

Welcome to the British Library's alpha open data portal.

As part of its work to open its data to wider use, the British Library is making copies of some of its datasets available for research and creative purposes.

We aim to describe collections in terms of their data format (images, full text, metadata, etc), licences, temporal and geographic scope, originating purpose (e.g. specific digitisation projects or exhibitions) and collection, and related subjects or themes.

This site is in the early stages of development. If you have questions or feedback about this site or our open data work, please email digitalresearch@bl.uk. We'd also love to hear what you've done or made with the data.

A collection of datasets released by the British Library

portraitsviewsplaybills - comprises 2 datasets.

india-office-records - comprises 1 dataset.

taverns-signs - comprises 3 datasets.

portraits-views-playbills - comprises 1 dataset.

advertisements - comprises 6 datasets.

dig19cbooks - comprises 13 datasets.

Each dataset may have its own licencing conditions and re-use stipulations, so please check their pages for more information.

Ask me for a demo!

BL Labs Competition

BL Labs Competition finalists for 2016

- **Black Abolitionist Performances and their Presence in Britain**
- *Hannah-Rose Murray, PhD student at the University of Nottingham*

- **SherlockNet: Using Convolutional Neural Networks to automatically tag and caption the British Library Flickr collection**
- *Luda Zhao, Brian Do and Karen Wang, students from Stanford University, California*

Political Meetings Mapper

"I was able to do in minutes with a python code what I'd spent the last ten years trying to do by hand!"

-Dr. Katrina Navickas, BL Labs Winner 2015

Political Meetings Mapper

Video: <https://youtu.be/XabsuyNkD5s>

How did we do it?

- Redo the OCR of original image files using Abbyy Finereader 12

OCR

Geo-code

- Python code to extract place names &
- geo-code places using a gazetteer

- Python code with regex to extract dates
- Basic NLP to calculate the dates of words like 'tomorrow'

Date

Spatial Humanities

'Being able to link the map and the underlying text allows us to understand how patterns vary from place to place.'

Combining Text Analysis and Geographic Information Systems to investigate the representation of disease in nineteenth-century newspapers, Lancaster

BL Labs Bi-Annual Competition & Awards

LIBRARY
HSLIRB

The 2016 British Library Labs Awards deadline is **5 September**.

'A million images' on Flickr Commons

The British Library profile banner features a circular logo on the left with the text 'BRITISH LIBRARY' in white on a red background. To the right of the logo, the text 'The British Library' is displayed in a large, white, serif font. Below this, a smaller white box contains a plus sign and the word 'Follow'. Further down, the text '22.9k Followers · 28 Following' is shown in a smaller white font. The background of the banner is a dark, textured image of a bookshelf filled with books.

Photostream

Albums

Favorites

Groups

More ▾

Highlights from the Mechanical Curator
98 photos · 245,995 views

Children's Book Illustration, found by the community from the Mechanical Curator Collection
1005 photos · 80,996 views

Book Covers found by the community from the Mechanical Curator Collection
812 photos · 39,951 views

Space & Science Fiction, found by the community from the Mechanical Curator Collection
412 photos · 41,238 views

Musical Instruments
103 photos · 9,123 views

Flora, found by the community from the Mechanical Curator Collection
860 photos · 46,825 views

Illustrated Letters & Typography, found by the community from the Mechanical Curator Collection
1505 photos · 37,624 views

Cycling, found by the community from the Mechanical Curator Collection
147 photos · 19,016 views

Mario Klingemann
'556 Minerals'

'Grassroots' projects

Welcome to FreeBMD.

FreeBMD is an ongoing project, the aim of which is to transcribe the Civil Registration index of births, marriages and deaths for England and Wales, and to provide free Internet access to the transcribed records. It is a part of the FreeUKGEN family, which also includes [FreeCEN](#) (Census data) and [FreeREG](#) (Parish Registers). To search the records that have so far been transcribed by FreeBMD click on the **Search** button below.

The recording of births, marriages and deaths was started in 1837 and is one of the most significant resources for genealogical research. The transcribing of the records is carried out by teams of dedicated volunteers and contains index information for the period 1837-1983, **BUT WE HAVE NOT YET TRANSCRIBED THE WHOLE PERIOD**. A breakdown by event and year can be viewed [here](#).

Donate

FreeBMD is exactly that - FREE. We do not make any charge whatsoever for use of the site. FreeBMD is a registered [charity](#) and our objective is to provide free online access to the [GRO Index](#). However, FreeBMD costs money to run and if you would like to make a donation by PayPal click on the button to the left. For other methods of making donations to FreeBMD please see [here](#).

Search

View Images

Information

Join FreeBMD

'Transcribers' Page

The FreeBMD Database was last updated on Thu 30 Oct 2014 and currently contains 242,129,588 distinct records (308,090,800 total records). On Mon 17 Nov 2014 FreeBMD users did 175,397 searches. ([More information](#))

Oxfordshire Family History Society

Transcribed Wills

About OFHS	Visit OFHS	OFHS Services	Web Resources
OFHS material	Transcribed Wills	Oxon & beyond	Useful Web Sites

This area of the OFHS web site contains the transcribed texts of wills, administrations and other testamentary documents, relating to Oxfordshire, which have been generously donated by their transcribers. Do you have any that you would be prepared to donate? If so, please click [here](#) for contact details.

Testator Index	Index of Persons Mentioned
A - Z	A B C D-F G H I-K L M-O P Q-R S T U-W X-Z ?
Search for Surnames matching a Specific Pattern <input type="text"/> <input type="button" value="Search"/>	
The search pattern may be a single surname, or may use a Regular Expression to match a set of alternative spellings for the surname. If you are not familiar with the concept of Regular Expressions, click here for an explanation.	

For Help Using These Pages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See Notes for Users if you are a first time visitor to these pages. • See Notes for Transcribers if you have any transcripts which you would be prepared to donate. • See Glossary for an explanation of some unusual words found in wills. • See Regular Expressions to learn about patterns which may be used to search for surnames. • See Probate on the GENUKI web site for general background information on finding wills. • See Oxford Wills before 1858 for specific information about Oxfordshire wills.

Location of Original Documents
<p>The majority of the transcripts presented here will be from originals held in one of two places, as indicated in the heading of the transcript:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ORO or OHC - designates Oxfordshire Record Office (ORO) or Oxfordshire History Centre (OHC) where you will find wills proved locally, when the deceased's property was all within the diocese. During 2011, Oxfordshire Record Office was renamed Oxfordshire History Centre and the web address changed. The link here will direct you to their new web site at: http://www.oxfordshire.gov.uk/oxfordshirehistory Scans of the original probate documents held at Oxfordshire History Centre may be purchased directly from OHC via the Staff-operated copying service on their web site. • Scans of the original probate documents held at Oxfordshire History Centre, are also available from Findmypast as part of their collection of England & Wales Published Wills & Probate Indexes 1300-1958

Participatory history as learning

- Constructive environments for learning and mastering skills
 - Palaeography
 - Tagging / classification
 - Source familiarity
 - Biographical research
 - Database and web design
 - Data collation, analysis, interpretation
 - Extended research projects

MarineLives digital pop up lab

Opens on July 4th 2016, two hours a week for ten weeks

Spaces for twelve volunteers

Collaborative experience for

historians, coders and computer scientists

Team one: working on semi-automated recognition of handwritten manuscripts

Team two: working on tailored search of historical documents

Team three: working on visualisation of historical data

@marinelivesorg <http://digitalpopuplab.org/>

Current most popular features

Each of the following three features (*a feature comprises several web pages*) can be accessed directly by clicking the text or images below:

Liz Knight's
latest researches:
A series featuring lacemaking

Tour of the
Market Place: 1800-1950s
Check out the video

Tom Garner's
WW1 Diary of his Service
on the Eastern Front

[Link to full content of Features](#)

Current most popular articles

Each of the following three articles can be accessed directly by clicking the text or images below:

LMS Railway at Olney
(Northampton-Bedford)
includes a video

Orchard House Nos 67 & 69 High Street
converted in 1904
for Joseph William Mann

Oliver Ratcliff's 1907
Book 'Olney, Bucks'
(*'Turning page'* version)

Conclusion

Kiitos / Thank you!

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